

PURPOSE, STRATEGY AND OUTCOME OF READING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article analyzes the purpose, strategy and outcome of reading process. Also, it shows the importance of reading skills development. There are given the following reading strategies as skimming, scanning and critique. It of them are opened by the author. And, one task was given as an example for clear comprehension.

Keywords: *purpose, strategy, outcome, reading process, skimming, scanning.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной научной статье анализируются цель, стратегия и результат процесса чтения. Кроме того, это показывает важность развития навыков чтения. Даны следующие стратегии чтения, такие как беглый просмотр, сканирование и критика. Всё это раскрывается автором. Одно задание было приведено в качестве примера для ясного понимания.

Ключевые слова: *цель, стратегия, результат, процесс чтения, беглый просмотр, сканирование.*

Reading is very important to get information in the world. Reading can make people to know from nothing to something. In English, reading is one of English skill besides listening, speaking and writing. Reading holds the in our life to search information or knowledge from textbooks, article or magazines written in English. Thus, the students should have good reading skills to help them in academic studies and to get information in the world. According to Musayeva and Tursunkulova¹ reading instruction often aims to develop students' decoding skills and knowledge of syntax or vocabulary for literal comprehension. Reading is closely connected with the pronunciation of human skills, which help to form the fugitive reading technique. Reading plays a major role in the process of learning a foreign language. Reading is the purpose and means of learning a foreign language. The growing interest in many

¹ Musaeva Munisa, Tursunkulova Aydin, Yugay Evgeniya Viktorovna THE ROLE OF READING SKILLS IN LEARNING A FOREIGN // Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. 2022. №12. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-role-of-reading-skills-in-learning-a-foreign> (дата обращения: 04.04.2023).

parts of the world in Modern Methods of teaching English brings with it the question of how it should be done – how curriculum, subject, matter, and methodology should differ from the familiar norms developed in the past¹. The goal of reading instruction is to give students the ability to read a foreign language, which is one of the practical purposes of studying of this discipline.

The process of reading can be viewed in terms of purpose, strategy and outcome. Purpose of reading is what makes the process necessary for the reader. Related to the purpose, a strategy of reading is chosen. The following strategies of reading are named to describe the process: skimming, scanning and critique.

Skimming is reading for the gist. It refers to the process of reading only main ideas within a passage to get an overall impression of the content of a reading selection. Here are mentioned some strategies on **How to Skim**:

- Read the title.
- Read the introduction or the first paragraph.
- Read the first sentence of every other paragraph.
- Read any headings and sub-headings.
- Notice any pictures, charts, or graphs.
- Notice any italicized or boldface words or phrases.
- Read the summary or last paragraph.

When to skim

Because skimming is done at a fast speed with less-than-normal comprehension, you shouldn't skim all the time. There are many times, however, when skimming is very useful. Suppose you are taking a presentation skills class and have to deliver an oral report in a few days about the first computers ever made. You locate six books and four newspaper articles about this topic. Because you must be ready soon, you do not have time to read each word, but you need a large quantity of solid information.

Skimming will help you locate the information quickly while making sure you use your time wisely. It will also increase the amount of usable material you obtain for your research².

Suppose you have an exam in a few days. You need to review the material you learned, but you don't want to reread everything. By skimming, you can quickly locate the information you haven't mastered yet and study only that material.

¹ Akhtamova Guzal, Nurullayeva Madina, Yugay Evgeniya Viktorovna THE MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH // Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. 2022. №12. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-modern-methods-of-teaching-english-1> (дата обращения: 04.04.2023).

² <https://www.utc.edu/enrollment-management-and-student-affairs/center-for-academic-support-and-advisement/tips-for-academic-success/skimming>

While reading, ask yourself the following questions to help you decide whether or not to skim. If you answer yes to any of these, then skimming is a useful tool.

1. Is this material non-fiction?
2. Do I have a lot to read and only a small amount of time?
3. Do I already know something about this?
4. Can any of the material be skipped?

If you have sufficient background knowledge or believe you don't need the information, then skip it! That's right - don't read it at all! Believe it or not, skipping material may sometimes be the best use of your time. Just because someone wrote something doesn't mean you have to read it. If you pick and choose carefully what you skim and skip, you will be pleasantly surprised at the large amount of information you can get through in a short period of time.

Scanning is reading for details. It is a reading technique to be used when you want to find specific information quickly. In scanning you have a question in your mind and you read a passage only to find the answer, ignoring unrelated information¹. Here are mentioned some strategies on **How to Scan**:

- State the specific information you are looking for.
- Try to anticipate how the answer will appear and what clues you might use to help you locate the answer. For example, if you were looking for a certain date, you would quickly read the paragraph looking only for numbers.
- Use headings and any other aids that will help you identify which sections might contain the information you are looking for.
- Selectively read and skip through sections of the passage.

When to scan

You scan when your aim is to find specific pieces of information. If you were doing the research for an oral presentation, you could scan the index of books, web sites, and reference materials. You would discover whether they contain any information you want and the pages where the information can be found.

In the past, you probably scanned without knowing you were doing it. Now with the information provided in this section, you can use scanning more intentionally and frequently. The more you practice, the more effective scanning will become. Finally, the most important benefit of scanning is its ability to help you become a more flexible reader. Scanning adds another high gear to your reading.

Because you may be used to reading every word and may be uncomfortable leaving some words out, you need to give yourself permission to overlook some words by

¹ <http://pioneer.netserv.chula.ac.th/~pkanchan/html/skim.htm>

skimming, scanning, and skipping material according to your reading purpose. **Critique** is reading for critical analysis and putting to verification the truth of what is written in the text¹.

As an example we can give such kind of activity to our students. See Table 1.

Table 1. Activity. Indicate which purpose, strategy and outcome would match the following short excerpts for reading

Text	Purpose	Strategy	Outcome
a) "Learners often make errors in good faith that their spelling is correct. The teachers act in good faith that the learners lack knowledge"	1. Pleasure	A/ Skimming	I. Ideas
b) "A growing social group are parents that behave like teenagers. They wear nose-rings, tongue-studs and squeeze into clothes for children"	2. Studies	B/ Scanning	II. Knowledge
c) "The study showed that perceptions of the waiting time in queues were 30 percent longer than the real waiting time in banks"	3. Job	C/ Critique	III. Opinions

It concludes that English teacher that use skimming and scanning in teaching English on the part of reading are gaining the successful outcomes of their students. Finally, know your context. There may be some texts that you are better off reading closely and thoroughly. Some professors specifically tell you that they include small details from the textbook on exams. You may have some classes that are just difficult to understand, and you may find that reading closely helps you comprehend concepts better. Before skimming, spend some time thinking about your classes, professors, and needs to determine if you have any texts you may need to read more closely.

¹ Yugay E.V. PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT IN LEARNERS OF DIFFERENT AGES // Интернаука: электрон. научн. журн. 2023. № 12(282). URL: <https://internauka.org/journal/science/internauka/282> (дата обращения: 05.04.2023). DOI:10.32743/26870142.2023.12.282.354274

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